

Modeling and Simulink Control System of Missile and Simulink by MATLAB

(Pemodelan dan Panduan Peluru Berpandu dan Sistem Kawalan Menggunakan MATLAB)

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ABSTRACT

For this project, the missile control system has been analyzed based on a model. All simulations are done using the MATLAB Simulink and m – file. As the main purpose of proposing this thesis is to introduce the aspects of missile control, all that have been written are the basic things in control. At the first stage, a crucial understanding of the airplane system is needed as it forms the basis for understanding the control aspect of a missile. Both systems are correlated in some aspects. The transfer functions from the airplane are used in the first few simulations and have been analyzed to get a better understanding of the flight principle. The next stage concerns the autopilot analysis, developed based on a model. The simulation is done to analyze the stability of the system. Some are simulated in trial and error to get the best result. To complete this thesis, further analyses are conducted, these include the seeker and the guidance law of proportional navigation. A seeker is mainly an observer developed to get some information on the target such as the closing distance and target acceleration. All the above aspects form a complete control loop for the missile-based on acceleration command.

Keywords: Missile, autopilot, guidance law of proportional navigation, Matlab and Simulink simulation

ABSTRAK

Di dalam projek ini, satu sistem kawalan peluru berpandu telah dikaji dan dianalisis berdasarkan model sedia ada. Semua hasil simulasi dilakukan menggunakan perisian Matlab khususnya Simulink dan fail – m. Oleh kerana penulisan tesis ini bertujuan sebagai satu pengenalan kepada kawalan peluru berpandu, semua yang dipaparkan adalah merupakan asas – asas dalam sistem kawalan. Pemahaman dalam aspek kawalan kapal terbang menjadi asas kepada kawalan peluru berpandu kerana kedua – duanya saling berkaitan. Fungsi pindah yang digunakannya diambil daripada fungsi pindah kapal terbang seterusnya digunakan bagi tujuan simulasi. Peringkat seterusnya adalah analisis bagi juruterbang automatik yang dibangunkan berdasarkan kepada model. Bagi melengkapkan tujuan tesis ini, kajian dilanjutkan merangkumi analisis bagi penjejak dan aturan kawalan navigasi berkadar. Penjejak merupakan satu pemerhati) yang memberikan maklumat tertentu sasaran seperti jarak dan pecutan. Kesemua bahagian ini akan membentuk satu sistem kawalan lengkap bagi sebuah peluru berpandu, berdasarkan arahan pecutan.

Katakunci: Peluru-berpandu, autopilot, aturan kawalan navigasi berkadar, simulasi Matlab dan Simulink

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, advances in science and technology are growing in most countries in the world. The difference between a missile and a rocket is in terms of the driving system or the target system. Basic missiles are divided into two types, namely cruise missiles and ballistic missiles. A cruise missile has been used more widely as compared to a ballistic missile. This is due to the simpler manufacturing process as opposed to the ballistic missile and more suitable for combat situations.

After World War I, the British and the Europeans developed and tested automatic control systems on both yachts and twin-engine aircraft, the system was exhibited and tested in 1916. Change has been made to their flying bombs by using radio controls to intercept Zeppelins and carry out ground target attacks (Werrell, Kenneth P 1985

At the early stage of World War II, the Germans succeeded in developing their first cruise missile and named (V-1 flying bomb) (Steven J Zaloga 2011). Ballistic missiles and V-2 ballistic missiles, from both types of missiles are using mechanical automatic flight systems (Steven J Zaloga 2013). Many nations or superpowers have conducted various missile technology studies during post-WWII to ensure that no one is left behind for national security and defense. In the field of missile weapons, the U.S. military has taken an active role in leading the field. There are various interventions in perfecting Dr. Werrell's manuscript in 1982 (Werrell, Kenneth P 1985).

This study aims to simulate a missile control system using a MATLAB/Simulink simulation and provide some basis for understanding the missile development process to enable our country to catch up with the pace of other developed countries.

A brief literature review from previous researchers provide explanations to the concepts and laws of missiles and results for reference. The material is essential for the simulation of the missile control system according to the desired criteria. The missile model used is obtained from the previous thesis and the calculation of each variable function that must be available in the control system. The previous study was concerned more with the simulations from a major reference to be used in the missile control system. This study will enhance the previous system to obtain satisfactory results from the MATLAB simulations. Prior to the simulation process, the existing MATLAB Simulink example for the missile control system is studied. This can be done by typing in the "(aero_guidance)" command to get the base of the missile control system from launch to the target intersection point.

METHODOLOGY

Simulation is performed using the Matlab/Simulink environment. Although the initial plan is to use Arduino to simulate the environment and the servo system, only software-based simulation can be performed due to time restrictions. To design and develop the missile homing control systems, several references were used. The goal of the missile in the homing system is to hit the target. Thus a target position is required before constructing the complete homing control system. As the dynamic model for the missile is in the Polar Coordinate System, the target position in the Cartesian Coordinate must change to the Polar Coordinate or vice versa. The first step before the completion of the home control system is shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. Block diagram target position and function parameters missile to target separation

In order to make a complete homing control system, there are three components that need to be developed. By invoking "aero_guidance" in the MATLAB command will leads to a simple example of missile guidance. By using body simulation as an example, a new system with better, safer and more complicated can be constructed. After the target position above, as in Fig. 1, a servo tracker system as in Figure 2 need to be developed as the first system block.

FIGURE 2. Block diagram tracker servo system

In the block diagram, the tracker servo system consists of many other subsystems. For this subsystem, the tracker and sightline rate comprises of two other sub-subsystem. Refer to Figure 3, for the tracker and sightline rate simulation. The other two important sub-subsystems which are; a target tracker and missile stabilizer

FIGURE 3. Block diagram tracker and sightline rate

Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the subsystem for two main system for make the successful homing control system. So, this tracking loop and stabilization loop are build and following the tracker and sightline system are develop. This two subsystem is used for the target and for the missile.

FIGURE 4. Block diagram tracking loop

FIGURE 5. Block diagram stabilization loop

The other subsystem from the tracker servo system is for target acquisition. This subsystem is to ensure that the gimbal that is provided in the simulation is in parallel with the beam width to make the successful missile. Figure 6 shown the system was created and one more subsystem in this tracker servo system which is subsystem for range and closing velocity estimates in Figure 7.

FIGURE 6. Block diagram target acquisition

FIGURE 7. Block diagram range and closing velocity estimates

Next step of this procedures is to build and create second servo system which is the guidance. There are two subsystem in this servo system and it consist of an additional block of simulation to make it better and safe to launch in simulation, or in the real missile. Figure 8 shown the servo system for guidance got an addition.

FIGURE 8. Block diagram guidance servo system

Before the presence of guidance servo system, there are two other subsystem to be built first before we get the guidance servo system. Initially, a subsystem is built from a state flow to make a guidance processor. This guidance processor requires an intake and process the system following the state flow. This will make a new product to make other process. Figure 9 shows the state flow for guidance processor.

FIGURE 9. State flow diagram guidance processor

This is last subsystem in this second servo system, this subsystem very importance to make this missile safety to using and just hit the target. This fuze system taking the miss distance from the actual target read and calculate by function block. If this missile calculate the miss distance far from target this missile will stop simulation. Which means, the missile cannot

launch in the real. FIGURE 10 shown the fuze system.

FIGURE 10. Block diagram fuze system

Last but not least, this is the last servo system for homing control system. This last servo system called servo system of airframe and autopilot. This servo system got three subsystem and two function block parameter. The function block parameter to make this control system reading the data one for the atmosphere and another one for fin actuator. For the three subsystem in this servo system must be build it first to develop this servo system. Three main system we must know about it to develop homing control system. Following the combination of three subsystem and two function block parameter for FIGURE 11 below.

FIGURE 11. Block diagram servo system of airframe and autopilot

First subsystem are sensor system. This system taking the reading from two sensor which is rate gyro and accelerometer. This sensor taking reading of this two type of sensor for calculate rate gyro for tracker servo system track accurate target and another sensor accelerometer take reading to autopilot for setting the missile itself.

FIGURE 12. Block diagram sensor system

The second subsystem for this servo system complicate a bit but already fix it by alter the block for subsystem aerodynamic. This subsystem got another subsystem in their system and have two function block parameter for equations of motion and incidence and airspeed. FIGURE 13 shown the diagram of subsystem aerodynamics and equations of motion. Following the FIGURE 14 are subsystem aerodynamics of this subsystem.

FIGURE 13. Block diagram aerodynamics and equations of motion

FIGURE 14. Block diagram aerodynamics

Last subsystem for this servo system are, autopilot system. This missile got autopilot system which means it can afford to control itself after launch by put this autopilot system for this homing control system. FIGURE 15 shown the block diagram of autopilot system working flow. There are many function block parameter used for build up this autopilot system.

FIGURE 15. Block diagram autopilot

Lastly, all this homing control system connected to the 3D of animation because this project just taking result by visual animation to predict the missile hit the accurate target. FIGURE 16 shown the ending of this system generate the animation 3D only. For those whose worthy to test the real missile can using this homing control system.

FIGURE 16. Block 3D of animation and animation figure

RESULTS

The visual of 3D animation are result to prove the homing control system are safety to use or not. This system can be only hit the target accurately by taking miss distance predicted by this system. This 3D animation can be change to real missile by change the block to output system at true missile but only the worthy person for good reason. Another result it be data came from graph given after this 3D animation. The collected data to making more improvement of this system.

FIGURE 17. 3D animation visual

This are the following collected data from the result. For FIGURE 18 there is four data taken in graph for normal acceleration, incidence α , Mach number and fin demand all four data versus by time. This data taking in time from intial which is the missile launch to the end of time wherse the missile hit the target. There is the range of all this data time. To make the perfect missile by refer the data give after run simulation and make change in the homing control system to get the data required.

FIGURE 18. Graph of (normal acceleration, incidence α , Mach number and fin demand) vs. time

Last for this result, the data appears for gimbal and look angel versus time to show how the missile operate after launch. There are change for gimbal and look angel that control by fin demand and autopilot to accurate hit the target. Another graph shown in FIGURE 19 are the missile and target trajectories to predict the collision point in unit meter.

FIGURE 19. Graph of gimbal and look angel vs. time and missile and target trajectories

DISCUSSION

The modeling and Simulink control system of Missile are developed. Homing control system build up for make the predict result before do the real launch missile. By using the data given after run the simulation we can predict the better and follow what we need while launching the missile. By using MATLAB Simulink everyone can make their own modeling design of missile but the reference to complete this project quite hard to find because this project not comfortable to everyone.

While develop this project, there is some error before get the wanted result. This error occur based on the wrong block diagram used in the simulation. The problem in this project that I learn from this project are tools block must do proper. Some time there is no block which I needed in this project but by alter and use different block combination to get wanted block.

CONCLUSION

In this study case, by developed this project we can take an advantage for improve our nation on defense. This project also pop up the bubble of society to study and approved this destroyer for good. By using MATLAB Simulink everyone can study simply about missile only front laptop it's not cost too much to study and developed this missile using Simulink first. No need to cost and waste our nation money to test real missile instead MATLAB Simulink. Herby, this project can open society mind to study future and approved also can cost our military budget and saving our state savings.

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